

The Moderating Role of Brand Experience on the Relationship between Social Media Marketing Activities and Brand Equity in Jordanian Five Star Hotels

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History Received: August 23, 2020 Accepted: October 18, 2020	<i>The tourism sector in Jordan has a major role in the national economy. So, this study aims to determine the role of Social media marketing activities as an independent variable and the brand experience as moderator in the relationship between Social media marketing activities and brand equity in its dimensions (image of the brand, perceived quality, and loyalty to the market) as an approved variable in the five-star hotel sector operating in Jordan. The data collection was carried out by means of a self-administered questionnaire designed for the purpose of the current study. 300 forms had distributed and only retrieved (206) but only (204) valid forms and excluded two invalid ones. An analytical descriptive approach, Correlation and regression analyses were used to test the two hypotheses. The study showed that there is an impact of social media marketing activities on brand equity. Dimensions (image of the brand, perceived quality and loyalty to the brand), and that there is an effect of the moderator, the effect of the brand experience in the relationship between social media marketing activities and trademark ownership rights, as the effect was raised from 13.9% to 59.3%, as with the modified variable entering the brand experience The effect was raised by 45.5%, which indicates the important role of the customer's experience with the brand in the impact of Social media marketing activities on the formation of the brand's value. These results would help the decision maker to take seriously steps to improve the hotel sector in Jordan.</i>
Keywords Social Media, brand experience, brand equity, Jordan.	
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1. Introduction

As of late, social media marketing has become universal and generally significant for social networking, content sharing and online accessing. Because of its unwavering quality, consistency and instantaneous highlights, social media opens a wide spot for businesses, for example, online marketing. Marketing which happens through social media is known as social media marketing. Social media marketing has made workable for organizations to reach focused on consumers effectively, adequately and instantly (Nadaraja, and Yazdanifard, 2013).

One of the common channels of communication that organizations have as of late applied in their marketing activities is social media. It very well may be defined as an online application program, stage, or broad communications instrument that encourages interaction, collaboration, or content sharing between clients as a rule (Kim and Ko, 2012). The impact of social media on consumer's conduct includes a wide range of activities ranging from informing, sharing thoughts and perspectives to get mindfulness and understanding, and imagine post-buy conduct without purchasing (Tatar and Erdoğan, 2016). Furthermore, because of social media marketing activities, businesses can perform activities, for example, creating their very own brand profiles and introducing online client assistance, item information and uncommon offers in a basic, modest, and continuous way (Breitsohl et al., 2017).

Social media marketing is not quite the same as traditional strategies for marketing; therefore, it requires exceptional attention and procedure building to accomplish brand equity. Social media marketing is identified with relationship marketing, where the organizations need to move from "trying to sell" to "making connections" with the consumers. Social media marketing is likewise more sincere in its communication with the consumers, trying to show what the brand is rather than trying to control its picture. Finally, the present clients are all the more remarkable and occupied; therefore, organizations ought to be reachable and accessible in each social media communication channel, for example, Face book, Twitter, Blogs, Forums whenever (Gordhamer, 2009). Therefore, in request to contact the correct objective gatherings with social media marketing and in request to construct more noteworthy brand equity, the organization should concentrate on numerous social media stages (Pelamo, 2018). Therefore, Social media alludes to the methods for interactions among individuals wherein they make, offer, and trade information and thoughts in virtual networks and organizations. Kaplan and Haenlein (2012) defined social media as "a gathering of Internet-put together

applications that worked with respect to the philosophical and mechanical foundations of Web 2.0 and that permit the creation and trade of client produced content. Furthermore, social media rely upon portable and online advancements to make profoundly interactive stages through which individuals and networks share, co-make, talk about, and adjust client produced content. It introduces generous and unavoidable changes in communication between organizations, networks, and individuals.

In term of branding, it has accepted extraordinary essentialness in numerous organizations around the world (Chen and Green, 2009). It is a basic for a wide range of organizations because of saw benefits like differentiation, profitability, client dependability and upper hand (Keller, 2013). In this way, Leone et al. (2006) defined Brand equity that it is emotional for clients and intangible appraisal of the brand, well beyond its unbiasedly seen esteem. Three key drivers of brand equity are client brand mindfulness, client brand perspectives, and client perception of brand morals. Brand equity is worked through picture and meaning. Other researchers, for example, (Capon 2013) have defined brand equity as the consumer's response to a brand's actions comparative with competing brand's actions. Brand equity is in this way generally saw as a vital result of branding that includes key preferences that accumulate to a brand comparative with its rivals (Wang and Sengupta, 2016).

The conceptualizations of consumer-based brand equity have mainly gotten from intellectual brain science and information economics (Rahman et al., 2018). In his client based brand equity definition, Keller features the significance of marketing programs in linking consumers' mindfulness, wanted musings, feelings, perceptions, and opinions to a brand (Huang and Cai, 2015). Until now, brand equity has gotten only restricted attention in the context of social media marketing and its viability, regardless of a couple of striking exceptions (Kim and Ko, 2012).

On the other hand, brand experience quantifies the quality of each experience dimension evoked by the brand, when contrasted with the particular experiences which are estimated in investigations of client experience. It is critical to gauge experience dependent on client viewpoint on the grounds that an exceptional brand experience will fill in as a sustainable upper hand in hotels industry (Ong, Salleh, and Yusoff, 2015). Client experience research in the hotels industry commonly gauges experience with the environment, food quality, and value reasonableness (Ali, Amin, and Cobanoglu, 2016). This infers concentrates on client experience in the hotels industry have generally overlooked the way that experience may likewise get from sensation, affection, social, and intellectual from the point of view of branding (Brakus, Schmitt, and Zarantonello, 2009).

In Jordan, the tourism sector is one of the main contributors of the Jordanian economy (Central Bank of Jordan, 2019). Tourism income increased by 10.2% in the year 2019 (\$USA5.8) billion, compared to \$USA5.17 billion in 2018. This is because the number of overnight tourists increased by 8.9% during the year 2019 which was 5.36 million tourists, compared to 2018 (Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities 2019). Also, in 2019, the number of five-star hotels in Jordan was (37) hotels and 48.6% (18 hotels) of them were in Amman. The number of beds that were occupied by tourists was (6319297) beds, of which (3619707) beds were in five-star hotels, which represented 58.2% of the total occupancy, indicating the interest of tourists in the accommodation service in five-star hotels (Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities, 2019).

In January 2020, the income of the travel industry came to about JD362 million which is about \$USA510.3 million. It shows that the increasing was 11.4% contrasted with the main month of 2019 which was 9.1%. This is on the grounds that the absolute number of travelers increasing by 12.1% to arrive at 478.9 thousand sightseers, contrasted with the very month in 2019 (Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities, 2019). Regarding geographical distribution, the quantity of travelers from the Arab Gulf states was 23.9%, Arab nations by 20.1%, trailed by the Asian nations by 18.7%, the European Union nations 15.4% and the USA 11.7 % (Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities, 2019). This implies 42% of the vacationers were from the Arab nations (Saudi Arabia (14.4%), Iraq (6.4%) and Palestine (4.7%)). Additionally, the Non-inhabitant Jordanians was a 35.1%.

All these information uphold the need of moving towards social media from the said the travel industry foundations, particularly five-star hotels, to increase the information and experience of their clients, which in turn increases the brand equity of these institutions, where it is seen that a pace of 64.9 % of the pioneers of five-star hotels are outsiders and Arabs, that is, from outside Jordan. Therefore, social media will be the main apparatus for communicating with them and overcoming the topographical and separations, particularly with the increasing significance of social media for consumers in searching for their vacationer destinations and administrations that they need to obtain.

The point of the investigation is to feature the degree of the influence of social media marketing activities on the brand equity, just as the degree of the brand experience in dealing with the brand equity in the formation of the estimation of the brand with the client. This is on the grounds that the significance of social media in the consumer crowd in a period in which innovation has become the ace of the situation that was exploiting it in a distinct manner, and the social media, particularly the social media marketing, has created to turn into the most significant instrument and use by people in general and by institutions. Additionally, it is to distinguish the role that the brand experience consider plays its impact as an arbitrator factor for the influence of social media on the estimation of the market among five-star lodging clients. Consequently, the reason for this examination is to

gauge the impact of social media on the estimation of the brand equity among clients of five-star hotels in Amman. The motivation behind the investigation can be accomplished by answering the following questions:

- 1) What is the degree of social media use by clients of five-star hotels in Amman in forming the estimation of the brand equity they have?
- 2) What is the degree of social media use by five-star hotels to assemble the estimation of the brand among its clients?
- 3) What is the impact of client brand experience as arbitrator in the relationship between Social media marketing activities and brand equity in five-star hotels operating in the Jordanian capital, Amman?

Examination that examines social media marketing impacts from the viewpoint of branding writing is additionally still mainly exploratory and needs exact investigations (Hollebeek, Glynn, and Brodie, 2014). Until now, brand equity and brand experience has gotten only restricted attention in the context of social media marketing and its viability, regardless of a couple of outstanding exceptions (for example Kim & Ko, 2012). Therefore, this examination contributes to earlier writing by offering a thorough system and examines how social media marketing endeavors impact brand equity and brand experience in five-star hotels. Furthermore, the essentialness of the examination is risen up out of the theoretical point of view through the writing on the estimation of the brand when all is said in done and the administration and relationship of the social media in its composition among clients specifically, just as the significance of the client experience with the brand in creating the estimation of the brand as a changed factor through the adoption of institutions by and large and five-star hotels as a rule for social media in building the estimation of the brand specifically. All in all, the current examination tries to accomplish the main objective identified with measuring the social media over the estimation of the brand equity overall (combined and individually). From this, it prompts other sub-objectives spoke to in measuring the degrees of study factors.

The rest of this article is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses the past studies. Section 3 describes the data sources, framework of the study and methodology. Section 4 deals with empirical results discussion. Conclusions and policy implications are discussed in section 5.

2. Literature review

Social Media Marketing (SMM):

Social media marketing is the marketing techniques that savvy businesses are employing in request to be an aspect of an organization of individuals online (Williams, 2010). Business-to-consumer (B2C) advertisers rushed to understand the estimation of Facebook as a branding opportunity. Entertainment organizations, for example, film studios, book distributors, and music marks, were among the initial promoters on Facebook and that continue to have a significant presence. Social media marketing endeavors give advertisers wonderful chances to arrive at consumers in their social networks and assemble more personal relationships with them (Kelly, Kerr, & Drennan, 2010). Social media have changed the manner in which brand content is made, disseminated, and consumed, transferring the ability to shape brand pictures from advertisers to consumers' online connections and content (Tsai and Men, 2013).

According to Zahoor and Qureshi (2017) social media has a noteworthy role in developing brand equity and brand mindfulness. Kim and Ko (2012) portrayed extravagance brands' social media marketing endeavors as comprising five dimensions: entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and verbal. In a social media setting, marketing activities upgrade client based brand equity (Bruhn, Schoenmueller, and Schafer, 2012; Kim and Ko, 2012). According to Mangold and Faulds (2009), social media marketing actions are essential for the promotional blend in the new brand communication worldview. Bruhn et al., (2012) unveil that traditional just as social media communication significantly affect brand equity. While traditional media strongerly affect brand mindfulness, social media communication strongly influences brand picture. In the light of this discussion, this examination expects the social media marketing endeavors of extravagance brands to affect brand equity creation.

Brand Equity (BE):

The components of brand equity have been investigated for a long time as isolated constructs and the achievement of a brand. Aaker (1991) introduced the brand equity structure and his system included and combined the most notable components (for example reliability, mindfulness, quality and associations) and consequently, most of analysts have followed his model with some degree of modifications depending on the context (Tasci, 2018). A brand can be considered as a bunch of functional and emotional qualities which are novel and can furnish clients with ideal experience (De Chernatony, 2010). A fruitful brand is important, since it can empower advertisers to gain upper hands by facilitating potential brand extensions, developing versatility against contenders' promotional weights, and creating passage obstructions to contenders (Kim et al., 2008a; Rowley, 2009). Clients' abstract and intangible appraisal of the brand, well beyond its equitably seen esteem. Three key drivers of brand equity are client brand mindfulness, client brand mentalities, and client perception of

brand morals (Leone et al., 2006). Brand equity typically relies upon three key measures which are: the mentality of the consumer regarding that brand, brand mindfulness, and finally the corporate morals (Ashraf et al., 2018). When all is said and done, Brand equity is defined as the marketing impacts, or the worth added to the item, explicitly owing to the brand (Keller, 1993; Rangaswamy et al., 1993). In other words, brand equity is the contrast between the utility of the significant traits of a central branded item and the absolute utility of the brand (Yoo et al., 2001). Brand equity can be considered a blend of both client based brand quality (equity) and financial brand equity (Barwise, 1993). Financial brand equity alludes generally to the estimation of a brand for accounting purposes, while client based brand equity alludes to the clients' commonality and interesting associations with the brand in memory (Keller, 1993).

The discussion on whether marketing investments constitute intangible resources and how to esteem them has been available in the accounting writing for quite a long time (e.g., Hirschey and Weygandt, 1985) and in the marketing writing all the more as of late (e.g., Madden et al., 2006; Johansson et al., 2012). Over the most recent couple of years, in the multidisciplinary writing calls for more prominent accentuation on the reporting and revelation of non-financial measures, for example, on consumer loyalty, have been inspired by the broad perception that marketing endeavors are key drivers of firm worth (Srinivasan and Hanssens 2009; Livne et al., 2011). Specifically, late exploration stresses the significance of brand equity. The concept of brand equity has its origins in psychological brain research (Aaker 1991; Keller 1993, 2003) as a proportion of the long-term results accomplished by the investment made in the creation and strengthening of brands. Brand equity speaks to the consumers' perceptions and perspectives towards it. As noted in Campo et al. (2013), perceptions are, in turn, a function both of natural sources, for example, verbal recommendations, and of induced sources, similar to the brand positioning made by the firm and its marketing communication.

Earlier writing indicates that brand equity is a decent proportion of the adequacy of brand investments. Specifically, Keller (2003) interprets brand equity as an extension between the marketing endeavors devoted in the past to the creation of a brand and their future outcomes. Despite the fact that definitions of brands contrast, the underlying notion is that a brand is a distinctive name with which consumers have an elevated level of mindfulness and a willingness to follow through on either higher than otherwise normal costs or make higher than otherwise buy recurrence. A portion of the advantages of a brand name would be: more noteworthy dedication, less weakness to serious marketing actions and economic emergencies, bigger margins, less (more) flexible response to cost increases (diminishes), more prominent exchange cooperation and backing, increased marketing communication adequacy, or more prominent gracefully chain power. As contended in Barth et al. (1998), the net impact of all these positive consequences would be that brand equity furnishes a firm with a more elevated level of operating earnings after some time (comparative with otherwise unbranded firms). Nonetheless, not all costs incurred in promoting a brand bring about brand equity, in a similar way (Sehar, et al., 2019) investigated the effect of Social Media's Marketing on the brand equity of the consumers. The aftereffects of their investigation demonstrated that brands can improve their relationship with the clients by using social media locales.

Brand experiences (BEX):

Consumers look for brands which give them interesting and paramount experiences. The experience gave by brands is considered to be a significant method for achieving sustainable upper hand (Harris et al., 2017). Consumer and marketing research have demonstrated that experiences happen when consumers look for items, when they search for them and get administration, and when they consume them. Therefore, the concept of brand experience has gathered the attention of marketing supervisors as consumers look for brands that give them special and critical experiences (Carrizo-Moreira, et al., 2017). The experiences of consumers are the place esteem is focused in (Tynan et al., 2014), and therefore "the more a brand brings out various experience dimensions, the more fulfilled a consumer will be with the brand". In that capacity, the consumer isn't only paying for the item or administration, yet in addition for the experience, as they see an incentive in it (Machado et al., 2014)

The competition among hoteliers has compelled to search for better approaches to separate their brand from rival brands (Bailey and Ball, 2006; Kim, 2008). Additionally, Yesawich (1996) indicated that guests connected significance to brand while selecting a lodging. Successful brand the executives systems require creation of emblematic, emotional and intangible contrasts to make vital inn brand experiences which may in turn induce visitor steadfastness – an embodiment of brand building (Cai and Hobson, 2004; So and King, 2010). This suggests hotels must endeavor to make most ideal experiences for clients at each point of interaction through powerful marketing methodologies (Gilmore and Pine, 2002; Miao and Mattila, 2013).

Brakus et al. (2009) built up a brand experience scale for a wide assortment of brands (the two merchandise and administration brands). In any case, his examination considered hardly any inn brands. An inn brand is distinguished from other brands based on the context in which a guest experiences the lodging offering (Walls, 2013). Without a scale that estimates experiences of guests evoked by inn brand-related upgrades, hoteliers have

needed to depend on the overall brand experience scale which may not be a precise proportion of brand experience in context of the inn industry. Brand experience in the inn industry varies from general brand experience regarding up close and personal interaction and information trade, short distribution channel, uncertain standards, dependability and consistency, among others (Akbaba, 2006). Subsequently, an understanding of the experiences evoked through lodging brands is significant (Manthiou et al., 2016; Walls, 2013) as it would give new brand the executives viewpoints and insights to hoteliers, and examination here would enhance existing writing on cordiality.

According to Gilmore and Pine (2002) and Williams and Chinn (2006), the transition from the administration economy to the experience economy has huge implications for the friendliness and the travel industry. Nonetheless, "experience-related examination remains under-spoke to in the travel industry writing" (Ritchie et al., 2011). Indeed, not many investigations have endeavored to recognize and assess inn experiences. For instance, Walls (2013) explained lodging put together experiences and their influence with respect to consumers' apparent worth; these experiences are simple, personalized and esteem included and have an exceptional character (Gilmore and Pine, 2002). Client experiences with an inn brand additionally create lodging brand equity (Xu and Chan, 2010). Additionally, to win a separated position in the client's mind, hotels should give positive and novel experiences to their clients (Cai and Hobson, 2004).

Based on the above discussion and to achieve the aim and answering the questions of this study, we formulated two hypotheses.

H01: There is no significant effect of Social media marketing activities (SMM) on brand equity (BE).

H01.1. There is no significant effect of Social media marketing activities on brand image (BI).

H01.2. There is no significant effect of Social media marketing activities on perceived quality (PQ).

H01.3. There is no significant effect of Social media marketing activities on brand loyalty (BL).

H02: There is no significant effect of brand experience (BEX) as moderator in the relationship between Social media marketing (SMM) activities and brand equity (BE).

3. Data Sources and Methodology

The study's population is for (5) five-star hotels clients out of (18) hotels in Amman. A basic random example consisting 300 individuals from five-star hotels was chosen for this study. The information collection for this study was completed by methods for a self-administered questionnaire intended with the end goal of the current study. The questionnaire dependent on the five Likert scale to quantify the study factors and dependent on significant exploration on administration quality in writing (Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1985; 1988; Oliver and Swan, 1989; Carman, 1990; Sang and Bekhet, 2015). The review instrument contained two sections. The primary section tended to segment issues concerning respondents. Section 2 zeroed in on factors that are accepted to affect Brand Equity domains. Nonetheless, the structure of this study is formulized as in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The study's model.

The brand equity apparatuses are: brand picture, seen quality, and brand faithfulness. These domains are influenced by social media marketing activities and brand experience as arbitrator. The effect of social media marketing activities on genuine brand equity was estimated using a five-point Likert scale (1= strongly concur, 5= strongly oppose this idea). The sub-things for each brand equity domain are appeared in Table 1. The information obtained from the study were dissected using SPSS (Version 22). The time of distributing the questionnaire kept going from 15 October 2019 until 20 November 2019.

Correlation and regression investigations were utilized to test the two hypotheses.

To start with, graphic examination was utilized to investigate the general degree of perception on the Brand Equity domains. For this reason, the general composite mean score for all the domains was estimated by summing up the complete scores for every domain and then dividing it by the absolute number of things. Second, to determine the best arrangement of indicator domains in predicting real brand equity, a basic regression technique was utilized. Third, the relationships between the independent and ward factors, i.e., Social

Media Marketing Activities domains and Brand Equity domains, were examined using Pearson item second correlation coefficient (r). Preliminary investigation was performed to guarantee non-violation of the assumptions of ordinality, homogeneity and linearity.

Dependability was surveyed by measuring Cronbach's Alpha, whose coefficient for the brand equity domains was more than 0.80, indicating a decent degree of internal consistency among the things making it up (see Table 1). Also, as coefficient esteems are very delicate to the quantity of things in the scale, particularly when scales have less than 10 things (as for the situation of the current study), it is entirely expected to find very low coefficient Alpha (e.g., 0.5) (Pallant, 2007, Bekhet, Al-alak and El-refae, 2012). To guarantee this doesn't matter to our estimation, Briggs and Cheek (1986) suggested that an inter-thing correlation within the range (0.2–0.5) would propose a significant strong relationship among the things. In the current study, the inter-thing correlation was within this range, suggesting an extremely strong relationship among the things for every domain (see Table 1).

4. Results Discussion

4.1 Respondent Profile

From the 300 questionnaires distributed, 204 completed questionnaires were received and analysed in this study. The response rate was 68% (see Table 1). In term of gender perspective, the distributions between male and female respondents were fairly balance i.e. 49% male and 51% female. Majority of the respondents were well educated with 91% of them were university graduates and postgraduate. In term of income, 63% of the respondents were within the JD500–JD2000 per month.

Table 1: Demographic attributes of the respondents (n=204)

Variable	Respondents' profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	100	49
	Female	104	51
Age	< 30	29	14.2
	31-53	68	33.3
	36 - 40	43	21.1
	41 - 45	40	19.6
	> 46	24	11.8
Qualification	Diploma	17	8.3
	Bachelor Degree	66	32.4
	Master	53	26.0
	PhD	68	33.3
Monthly Income (JD)	< 500	20	9.8
	501 - 1000	80	39.2
	1001 - 2000	49	24.5
	> 2001	54	26.5

4.2 Descriptive and interrelationship

Table 2 provides the descriptive analysis for all the variables that are incorporated in the study. The overall mean score for the variables was measured by computing the overall composite mean scores for each domain. These mean scores indicate that the mean ranges between 1.27 and 1.39 for the independent variables.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics.

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Variables	No. of items	Mean	S. Deviation	Inter-items Coefficients	Variance	Cronbach's α
SMM	5	1.27	0.34	0.65	1.15	0.75
BI	4	1.38	0.37	0.57	1.16	0.77
PQ	4	1.35	0.36	0.58	1.17	0.77
BL	5	1.39	0.39	0.62	1.10	0.75
BEX	11	1.30	0.30	0.52	1.306	0.78

Furthermore, Table 3 shows that all variables of this paper were significantly and positively associated with the dependent variable, (see Table 2).

Table 3: Correlation Matrix.

Variables	SMM	BI	PQ	BL	BEX
SMM	1				
BI	0.378	1			
PQ	0.598	0.346	1		
BL	0.508	0.634	0.398	1	
BEX	0.467	0.383	0.451	0.327	1

Predictors of simple linear regression model was proposed to determine the relationship between social media marketing and brand equity domains as shows in Figure 1. These relationships would be used to reject or accept the hypotheses as formulized earlier.

4.3Hypothesis Testing

A Simple linear regression model is conducted to investigate the H01 hypothesis and sub-hypotheses of the Brand equity domains. Table 4 shows these results.

Table 4: Impact of Social Media Marketing Activities on Brand Equity domains.

Dependent Variable	Model Summary		ANOVA		Coefficient		
	R	R ²	F	Sig.	β	t	Sig.
BE	0.611	0.374	120.489	0.000	0.611	10.977	0.000
BI	0.373	0.139	32.554	0.000	0.373	5.706	0.000
PQ	0.596	0.355	111.142	0.000	0.596	10.542	0.000
BL	0.507	0.258	70.061	0.000	0.507	8.370	0.000

H01. There is no significant effect of Social media marketing activities on brand equity.

Table 4 shows that the correlation value is ($r = 0.611$), which indicates that the relationship between social media marketing activities and brand equity variables is generally considered a good relationship. Also, the (R^2) value indicates how much of the total variation in the brand equity can be explained by social media marketing activities. In this case, (37.4%) can be explained; while the remaining proportion (62.6%) can be explained by other variables are not included in the model. Overall, ANOVA reveals that $F = 120.489$ ($p \leq 0.05$), which indicates that the regression model statistically significant (a good fit for the relationship between social media marketing activities and brand equity). Furthermore, the Coefficients table provides the necessary information to predict the brand equity from social media marketing activities, as well as determine whether social media marketing activities contributes statistically significantly to the model. Besides that, Beta values for social media marketing activities has reached (0.611) which indicate that predicting (61.1%) of the brand equity from social media marketing activities. In other word, the results can be interpreted as (For every unit increase in social media marketing activities, there is a (61.1%) increases in the predicted the brand equity).

H01.1. There is no significant effect of Social media marketing activities on brand image.

From the Table 4, the correlation value is ($r = 0.373$), which indicates that the relationship between Social Media Marketing Activities and Brand Image is generally considered a good relationship. The (R^2) value indicates how much of the total variation in the brand image can be explained by Social Media Marketing activities. In this case, (13.9%) can be explained; while the remaining proportion (86.1%) can be explained by other variables are not included in the regression model. Also, ANOVA table shows that $F = 32.554$ ($p \leq 0.05$), which indicates that, overall, the regression model statistically significant (a good fit for the relationship between social media marketing activities in brand image). Furthermore, the table provides the necessary information to predict the brand image from social media marketing activities, as well as determine whether social media marketing activities contributes statistically significantly to the model. Besides, the result shows that predicting (37.3%) of the brand image from social media marketing activities. In other word, the results can

be interpreted as (For every unit increase in social media marketing activities, there is a (37.3%) increases in the predicted the brand image).

H01.2. There is no significant effect of Social Media Marketing Activities Perceived Quality.

Table 4 shows the relationship between the Social Media Marketing Activities and Perceived Quality is generally considered a good relationship (0.596). Also, the (R^2) value indicates how much of the total variation in the perceived quality can be explained by social media marketing activities. In this case, (35.5%) can be explained; while the remaining proportion (64.5%) can be explained by other variables are not included in the regression model. In addition, ANOVA table provides an F-test value, $F = 111.142$ ($p \leq 0.05$), which indicates that the regression model statistically significant (a good fit for the relationship between social media marketing activities and perceived quality). Also, the table provides the necessary information to predict the perceived quality from social media marketing activities, as well as determine whether social media marketing activities contributes statistically significantly to the model. Besides that, the result indicate that predicting (59.6%) of the perceived quality is from social media marketing activities. In other word, the results can be interpreted as (For every unit increase in social media marketing activities, there is a (59.6%) increases in the predicted the perceived quality).

H01.3. There is no significant effect of Social Media Marketing Activities in Brand Loyalty.

Referring to Table 4, the relationship between Social Media Marketing Activities and Brand Loyalty is generally considered a good relationship ($r = 0.507$) and the (R^2) value indicates how much of the total variation in the brand loyalty can be explained by social media marketing activities. In this case, (25.8%) can be explained; while the remaining proportion (74.2%) can be explained by other variables are not included in the model. According to the ANOVA table ($F = 70.061$ ($p \leq 0.05$)), the regression model statistically significant (a good fit for the relationship between social media marketing activities and brand loyalty). Overall, it provides the necessary information to predict the brand loyalty from social media marketing activities, as well as determine whether social media marketing activities contributes statistically significantly to the model. Besides, the social media marketing activities could be predicting (50.7%) of the brand loyalty from social media marketing activities. In other word, every unit increase in social media marketing activities, there is a (50.7%) increases in the predicted the brand loyalty).

H02. There is no significant effect of brand experience as moderator in the relationship between Social media marketing activities and brand equity.

Table 5 presents the results of a hierarchical multiple regression analysis based on two models. The results of the first model based on the first step reflected the value of the correlation value ($R = 0.373$). It indicates a positive correlation between social media marketing (SMM) activities and brand equity (BE).

Table 5: Results of hierarchical regression analysis

dependent Variable	Independent Variables	First step			Second step		
		β	t. value	Sig.	β	t. value	Sig.
Brand Equity	SMM	0.373	5.706	0.000	-	-	-
	BEX, SMM				1.701	14.989	0.000
	R	0.373			0.770		
	R ²	0.139			0.593		
	ΔR^2	0.139			0.455		
	ΔF	32.554			224.675		
	Sig. ΔF	0.000			0.000		

The results also show a significant impact Statistical significance for the social media marketing activities variable in the brand equity, where the value of ($F = 32.554$, p value = $0.000 < 0.05$). Also, the value of the determination coefficient ($R^2 = 0.139$) which indicates that SMM activities explains (13.9%) of the variance in the brand equity.

In the second step, the moderating variable (brand experience) was entered for the regression model, the value of the correlation value increased to ($R = 0.770$) and the same applies to the value of the determining coefficient R^2 where it increased by (45.4%) and this ratio is statistically significant, where the value of ($\Delta F = 224.675$, sig.

= 0.000 < 0.05) is also reliable. Also, the results confirm that impact of brand experience on improving the impact of SMM activities on the brand equity is significant ($\beta = 1.701$, t. value = 14.989, sig. = 0.000). Based on the above results, it rejects the second null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis. This means that brand experience has improve the relationship between SMM and brand equity when use it as moderating variable.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

The paper is investigated the role of Social media marketing activities as an independent variable and the brand experience as arbitrator in the relationship between Social media marketing activities and brand equity in its dimensions (picture of the brand, seen quality, and unwaveringness to the imprint) as an endorsed variable in the five-star lodging division operating in Jordan. This is on the grounds that the travel industry division in Jordan has a significant role in the national economy. A logical enlightening methodology has been applied in this study, and the study network is comprised of (5) five-star lodging clients out of (18) hotels in Amman, and 220 structures were recovered (204) of which were recovered. All in all, it tends to sum up the following scholarly outcomes:

- 1) The client brand experience variable has played a significant and impact role as mediator in the relationship between Social media marketing activities and the brand equity.
- 2) Social media has as of late become playing a significant role in creating the brand equity with its three dimensions (Brand picture - Perceived quality - Brand dependability) for the consumers.
- 3) The consequences of the exploration demonstrated that social media, notwithstanding its spread among consumers and its incredible role in promoting specifically and marketing when all is said in done, must zero in on searching to find techniques that empower the consumer to have aptitude since it is significance during the time spent building the brand equity in the mind of the consumers.

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